

Marie Ellen Dawson Biography by Brian Paul Kaess

Marie Ellen Dawson was born on December 4, 1945, in Illinois (presumably Chicago), to Margaret Jane Swartz and Talmage Edward Dawson. She had an older half-sister, Wanda Lou Dawson, who she apparently met in the 1950's. Marie spent most of her life in the Chicago area (Chicago and Evanston). She attended Evanston High School in her teens but did not graduate.

She met and married Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess (aka Gert Edwin Kaess in America) on September 30, 1967, in Chicago. It was said they were hippies who met at a Loyola frat party. She gave birth to identical twin sons in October 1967: Brian Paul Kaess and Garret Thomas Kaess. Neighborhoods she lived in may have included Rogers Park, Edgewater, Lakeview, Uptown, and Austin (later in a nursing home). The family may have taken a trip to either Wisconsin or Canada. Brian remembers falling out of Gerd's VW van and being saved by leaves on the ground—it must have been a fall trip. Brian and Garret (under age five) also recall running naked near a water fountain in the Chicago area. Their mother once pointed out when Brian "saved" Garret by running into a throng of pigeons that had surrounded him and pulling him to safety.

After Gerd died in 1972, Marie and the twins fell into abject poverty on the North Side of Chicago from 1972 to 1977. They lived on streets like Argyle and Birchwood. They received welfare support to get by. Marie attempted to work as a waitress, but she was often home. Occasionally, grandma Margaret helped Marie and the children with peanut butter sandwiches. She would take the twins to see Dr. Novak for medical checkups near Children's Memorial Hospital. One time, during a fire on Argyle Avenue in Uptown, Mom wrapped Brian in a blanket, carried him, as Garret followed, and led them outside the building during a serious residential fire at their building, thus literally saving her kids and herself. Mom was a hero! Brian remembers watching the fireworks celebrations over Lake Michigan for the USA Bicentennial in 1976. He and Garret watched the flickering lights from a window.

A bit of an *eccentric*, Marie enjoyed reading books like Ayn Rand's *The Fountainhead*, and she'd say controversial things like, "They're going to drop the bomb on the Jews!" The twins could only laugh. She would also like to say, 'Brian & Garret, I do declare!' - reflecting a bit of southern *verve*. Her religion was unclear, though she spoke of Episcopalians. She even took the kids to see *Race with the Devil* (1975), starring Peter Fonda, at the Uptown Theatre in Chicago. She was known to do unusual things, like taking oatmeal baths. In one scary episode, Marie chased Brian with a knife in the apartment, while Garret barricaded himself in the bathroom. Brian kept pounding on the bathroom door, 'Garret! Garret! Help! Help!' to no avail. Garret wouldn't budge to open the door. How Brian survived is a mystery.

By the mid-'70s, she had become *paranoid* and pulled the kids out of school for about two years. They were left to fend for themselves and learned to read using comic books. They had a pet gerbil they adored, goldfish, and a cat. Food insecurity was a real struggle, which is a gentle *euphemism* for starvation. Brian remembers better times when Marie took them for walks—wearing a skirt and army jacket—proudly strolling down sunny 1970s Michigan Avenue with her twins. She loved buying them stuffed animals too, and taking them to museums and carnivals.

In 1977, following allegations of neglect, Illinois DCFS took custody of the twins, and they were eventually made *wards of the State of Illinois* under grandma Margaret's care. A Chicago Police arrest report from an earlier year mentions her offense as neglect. The twins had already been "put through the system," staying at Uhlich Children's Home and with foster parents in Des Plaines, Illinois (the Larsens).

Afterward, Marie became increasingly helpless. She would occasionally stop by to see the twins. She was barred from staying overnight with them while they were living with grandma Margaret, though she did visit and would often smoke cigarettes. The reason for the restriction was unclear. One time, overwhelmed by frustration, she smashed a chair through Margaret's front window. Garret immediately sprang into action, chasing her down Hollywood Street, where they nearly came to blows. Fortunately, cooler heads prevailed. In later years, the twins reconciled with their mother and visited her with their own children. She was always proud of Garret's 'scholastic' achievement and Brian's military service. Maybe she didn't know Garret also served in the military and Brian went to college too!

Grandma Margaret said friends who knew her in high school said they didn't 'recognize' her in later adulthood. This was literally true, when she once was 'beat up' by a black person at the Wilson CTA stop, and lost some teeth as a result.

In the early 1990s, the twins lost contact with her until she resurfaced around 1993 in a nursing home on Sheridan Avenue in Uptown. Garret happily exclaimed, "I found Mom!" She was later moved to Columbus Park Nursing Center, where she lived out the rest of her days in the Austin neighborhood on Chicago's West Side. Her twins and their families visited her there. The last time Brian saw her was December 25, 2011, when she mentioned her birthdate (December 4, 1945) and marriage date (September 30, 1967). She seemed in a somber mood and a bit 'down' but otherwise okay.

Marie died around October 1, 2012, in Cook County, Illinois, from a massive heart attack. Nurses at Columbus contacted Garret in Indiana to let him know. They confirmed that 'yes, she passed.' Brian was living in Mexico when he got word of his mom's death and could only pray that she had not suffered much. Garret managed her estate and chose to donate her body to science.

A widow for most of her life, Marie's story truly embodied the *adage*: "Women and Children First!" It reminds one of the words from the Manichaeian Psalm Book: 'I found a rest wherein there is no toil, I found a joy wherein there is no grief...' ¹ We fervently pray the same was also true for Marie.

¹ Allberry, C.R.C. *A Manichaeian Psalm-Book*. Part II. Stuttgart: W. Kohlhammer, 1938, p.168.